

FINDING SECONDARY DATA FOR MY RESEARCH

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ECPR SSMT 2012

AGENDA

About secondary analysis

- issues to be dealt with (metadata standards)

Open access to scientific information

Availability of International survey data (weights)

(administrative data?)

What can I do with on-line tools?

Possibilities ([EUROLAB](#), summer schools/ [ESS courses](#), [DWB](#), [UKDA](#))

Re-using data

- follow-up research
- new research
- undertake research reviews
- scrutinise findings
- teach and learn

SECONDARY DATA AND SECONDARY DATA ANALYSIS

Secondary data, is data collected by someone other than the user. Common sources of secondary data for social science include censuses, organisational records and data collected through qualitative methodologies or qualitative research. Primary data, by contrast, are collected by the investigator conducting the research.

Secondary data analysis saves time that would otherwise be spent collecting data and, particularly in the case of quantitative data, provides larger and higher-quality databases that would be unfeasible for any individual researcher to collect on their own. In addition, analysts of social and economic change consider secondary data essential, since it is impossible to conduct a new survey that can adequately capture past change and/or developments.

[wiki, Secondary data, 31.7.2012]

SECONDARY DATA AND SECONDARY DATA ANALYSIS

Reasons for using secondary data could be divided in 3 groups (Hayman in Štebe, 1999):

- **Conceptual and content reasons** (comparison between different time periods; already tested questionnaires; extensive set of variables; international surveys; different purposes of use; has documentation)
- **Methodological reasons** (combination of different data sources; weakness – not knowing details of data collected; data quality)
- **Economic reasons** (saving time and money)

Key elements encountered in secondary analysis

? **Data access** and its usefulness

? Preservation of **confidentiality and privacy**, that was guaranteed by primary researcher

? Property **rights** and ownership of data

Ethics and consent

When collecting data researchers should:

- Inform participants **how research data will be stored, preserved, and used** in the long term
- Inform participants **how confidentiality will be maintained**, e.g. by anonymising data
- Obtain **informed consent**, either written or verbal, for data sharing

* Sample consent forms can be accessed at UKDA website (<http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>)

Primary or secondary?

Does it make sense for you **to collect your own data**?

If not, what **data sources are available** to you that will answer your research question(s)? **When?**

Does secondary data **include population / variables** of your interest.

Is the **quality of data** good?

Does it have **good documentations**?

DATA

Most of the data saved in Social Science data archives are **micro** and not macro data.

Importance of metadata description

CAN YOU UNDERSTAND/USE THESE DATA?

SPSS data view

	proddate	idno	cntry	tvtot	tvpol	rdtot	rdpol	nwsptot	nwsppol	netuse	ppltrst	pplfair	pplhl
1	02.02.2011	10202	BE	7	1	0	66	0	66	0	0	0	0
2	02.02.2011	10203	BE	7	2	7	3	0	66	0	6	7	7
3	02.02.2011	10207	BE	2	2	3	3	3	3	7	2	4	4
4	02.02.2011	10208	BE	7	2	2	2	2	2	0	3	6	6
5	02.02.2011	10302	BE	0	66	3	0	1	1	7	3	5	5
6	02.02.2011	10305	BE	0	66	0	66	1	1	0	5	5	5
7	02.02.2011	10306	BE	4	1	0	66	0	66	7	5	6	6
8	02.02.2011	10307	BE	6	3	2	2	3	2	7	8	8	8
9	02.02.2011	10309	BE	3	2	4	2	0	66	5	7	9	9
10	02.02.2011	10401	BE	3	2	7	4	1	1	5	7	7	7
11	02.02.2011	10402	BE	3	3	0	66	2	2	1	6	6	6
12	02.02.2011	10403	BE	6	5	6	2	1	1	0	5	8	8
13	02.02.2011	10408	BE	2	1	0	66	1	0	1	7	7	7
14	02.02.2011	10409	BE	7	3	7	2	2	1	5	6	7	7
15	02.02.2011	10505	BE	7	3	7	1	2	2	7	5	5	5
16	02.02.2011	10506	BE	3	2	7	2	0	66	7	7	8	8
17	02.02.2011	10607	BE	0	66	7	1	0	66	2	3	5	5
18	02.02.2011	10704	BE	7	2	7	0	0	66	0	6	3	3
19	02.02.2011	10707	BE	4	2	7	7	4	1	6	3	3	3
20	02.02.2011	10801	BE	4	2	7	1	2	1	1	5	7	7
21	02.02.2011	10806	BE	4	2	0	66	0	66	7	3	5	5
22	02.02.2011	10807	BE	2	3	0	66	0	66	2	3	4	4
23	02.02.2011	10902	BE	3	1	7	1	1	1	7	5	5	5
24	02.02.2011	10906	BE	3	1	7	2	1	1	7	3	5	5
25	02.02.2011	10907	BE	4	3	7	7	5	2	7	6	5	5
26	02.02.2011	11004	BE	5	2	7	4	2	2	7	4	6	6
27	02.02.2011	11005	BE	4	2	6	1	1	1	7	5	7	7
28	02.02.2011	11007	BE	5	3	7	2	2	1	7	8	8	8
29	02.02.2011	11008	BE	1	1	5	0	5	2	7	4	5	5
30	02.02.2011	11106	BE	7	2	7	2	3	1	6	7	8	8
31	02.02.2011	11107	BE	4	2	7	1	1	1	7	7	8	8

SPSS variable view

	Name	Type	Width	Decimals	Label	Values	Missing
1	name	String	7	0	Title of dataset	None	None
2	essround	Numeric	1	0	ESS round	None	None
3	edition	String	3	0	Edition	None	None
4	proddate	String	10	0	Production date	None	None
5	idno	Numeric	12	0	Respondent's identification number	None	None
6	cntry	String	2	0	Country	{BE, Belgium}...	None
7	tvtot	Numeric	2	0	TV watching, total time on average weekday	{0, No time at all}...	66 - 99
8	tvpol	Numeric	2	0	TV watching, news/politics/current affairs on average weekday	{0, No time at all}...	66 - 99
9	rdtot	Numeric	2	0	Radio listening, total time on average weekday	{0, No time at all}...	66 - 99
10	rdpol	Numeric	2	0	Radio listening, news/politics/current affairs on average weekday	{0, No time at all}...	66 - 99
11	nwspptot	Numeric	2	0	Newspaper reading, total time on average weekday	{0, No time at all}...	66 - 99
12	nwspopol	Numeric	2	0	Newspaper reading, politics/current affairs on average weekday	{0, No time at all}...	66 - 99
13	netuse	Numeric	2	0	Personal use of internet/e-mail/www	{0, No access at home or work}...	66 - 99
14	ppltrst	Numeric	2	0	Most people can be trusted or you can't be too careful	{0, You can't be too careful}...	66 - 99
15	pplfair	Numeric	2	0	Most people try to take advantage of you, or try to be fair	{0, Most people try to take advant...}	66 - 99
16	pplhlp	Numeric	2	0	Most of the time people helpful or mostly looking out for themselves	{0, People mostly look out for the...}	66 - 99
17	polintr	Numeric	1	0	How interested in politics	{1, Very interested}...	6 - 9
18	polcmpl	Numeric	1	0	Politics too complicated to understand	{1, Never}...	6 - 9
19	poldcs	Numeric	1	0	Making mind up about political issues	{1, Very difficult}...	6 - 9
20	trstprl	Numeric	2	0	Trust in country's parliament	{0, No trust at all}...	66 - 99
21	trstlgl	Numeric	2	0	Trust in the legal system	{0, No trust at all}...	66 - 99
22	trstplc	Numeric	2	0	Trust in the police	{0, No trust at all}...	66 - 99
23	trstplt	Numeric	2	0	Trust in politicians	{0, No trust at all}...	66 - 99
24	trstprt	Numeric	2	0	Trust in political parties	{0, No trust at all}...	66 - 99
25	trstep	Numeric	2	0	Trust in the European Parliament	{0, No trust at all}...	66 - 99
26	trstun	Numeric	2	0	Trust in the United Nations	{0, No trust at all}...	66 - 99
27	vote	Numeric	1	0	Voted last national election	{1, Yes}...	6 - 9
28	prtvtbbe	Numeric	2	0	Party voted for in last national election, Belgium	{1, Groen!}...	66 - 99
29	prtvtabg	Numeric	2	0	Party voted for in last national election, Bulgaria	{1, Koalitziaa za Balgariia}...	66 - 99
30	prtvtbch	Numeric	2	0	Party voted for in last national election, Switzerland	{1, Radicals}...	66 - 99

METADATA

A crucial part of making data **user-friendly, shareable** and with **long-lasting usability** is to ensure they can be understood and interpreted by any user. This requires clear data description, annotation, contextual information and documentation.

Good documentation for research data contains both study-level information about the research and data creation, as well as descriptions and annotations at the variable, data item or data file level.

Metadata are a subset of core data documentation, which provides standardised structured information explaining the purpose, origin, time references, geographic location, creator, access conditions and terms of use of a data collection.

[UK DA, 2012]

METADATA

Metadata for online data catalogues or discovery portals are often structured to international standards or schemes such as

Dublin Core,

ISO 11179,

Data Documentation Initiative (**DDI**),

Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard (METS) and

Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange (**SDMX**) – used in NSI's.

The DDI is an international XML-based descriptive metadata standard for social science data used by most social science data archives in the world.

metadata editors

CITING DATA

Users of our data **must acknowledge and cite data sources** correctly in all publications and outputs.

Data are a vital part of the scientific research process and proper citation should be a significant feature of research publications.

Data citation:

- acknowledges the author's sources
- makes identifying data easier
- promotes the reproduction of research results
- makes it easier to find data
- allows the impact of data to be tracked
- provides a structure which recognises and can reward data creators.

[[more:UK DA, 2012](#)]

OPEN ACCESS

OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding

...are meant to apply to **research data**, whether already in existence or yet to be produced, that are supported by **public funds** for the purposes of developing publicly accessible scientific research and knowledge.....

This kind of data should be publicly available.

.. in accordance with the objectives and principles, such as openness, transparency, legal conformity, formal responsibility, professionalism, protection of intellectual property, interoperability, quality and security, efficiency, accountability and others.

UNESCO - Open Access to Scientific Information

UNESCO promotes Open Access (OA), with particular emphasis on scientific information (**journal articles, conference papers and datasets of various kinds**) emanating from publicly funded research.

gesis

Leibniz-Institut
für Sozialwissenschaften

NSD EUROPEAN ELECTION DATABASE

CESSDA

UK • DATA
ARCHIVE

ICPSR INTER-UNIVERSITY
CONSORTIUM FOR
POLITICAL AND
SOCIAL RESEARCH

International research

ISSP

EUROBAROMETER

European Values Study

Atlas European Values

European Social Survey

CSES
COMPARATIVE STUDY of ELECTORAL SYSTEMS

MPC Minnesota Population Center

SHARE
Survey of Health, Ageing
and Retirement in Europe
50+ in Europe

ACP

About CESSDA

Member Organisations
Research & Development
Expert Seminars
Governance
Contact Information

Accessing Data

CESSDA Catalogue
Help on Searching Data
Thematic Data
Ordering Data

Sharing Data

Planning Data Collection
Managing Data
Depositing Data
Archival Process
Dissemination
Rights & Confidentiality

Related Resources

Networks, Other Archives
Conferences, Training
Multinational Surveys
Tools

Internal

Council of European Social Science Data Archives

CESSDA is an umbrella organisation for social science data archives across Europe. Since the 1970s the members have worked together to improve access to data for researchers and students. CESSDA research and development projects and Expert Seminars enhance exchange of data and technologies among data organisations.

Preparations are underway to move CESSDA into a new organisation known as CESSDA European Research Infrastructure Consortium (CESSDA ERIC).

A Gateway to Social Science Data

Collectively the constituent CESSDA member organisations serve some 30,000+ social science and humanities researchers and students within the European Research Area each year, providing access to 25,000 data collections, delivering over 70,000 data collections per annum and acquiring a further 1,000 data collections each year.

Locate and Access Data

The [CESSDA Catalogue](#) enables users to locate datasets, as well as questions or variables within datasets, stored at CESSDA archives throughout Europe. Data collections include sociological surveys, election studies, longitudinal studies, opinion polls, and census data. Among the materials are international and European data such as the European Social Survey, the Eurobarometers, and the International Social Survey Programme.

Share Your Data

Sharing of research data is of great value to the research community. To ensure that the data which you are collecting today can be used in the future, a data management plan needs to be considered from an early stage. CESSDA archives can assist in the design of such a plan. Researchers and data publishers are encouraged to publish their datasets in the CESSDA Catalogue.

Manifesto of The New Global Data Generation

CESSDA is one of the original signatories to the [Manifesto of the New Global Data Generation](#) that outlines three concrete and urgent problems that need to be solved if Europe wants to foster access and sharing of data.

Support the Manifesto of The New Global Data Generation

CESSDA is one of the original signatories to the Manifesto that outlines three concrete and urgent problems that need to be solved if Europe wants to foster access and sharing of data. [\[more...\]](#)

Call for Presentations: CESSDA Expert Seminar 2012 "Data Acquisition and License Agreements"

The annual CESSDA Expert Seminar will take place in Tampere, Finland, on October 4-5. We are now inviting presentations and talks on all aspects of the acquisition process. [\[more...\]](#)

DwB Training Course: Learn how to work with EU-LFS

Data without Boundaries organizes, in cooperation with Eurostat, a series of three day training courses on integrated Eurostat datasets. This first course will focus on the European Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) and will be hosted by GESIS (Mannheim, Germany) on July 18-20, 2012. [\[more...\]](#)

CESSDA General Assembly 2012 focused on becoming an ERIC

The annual CESSDA GA meeting, held in Gothenburg in April, had a packed agenda. In 2012, CESSDA will focus on

CESSDA

COUNCIL OF EUROPEAN SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ARCHIVES

- [-] CESSDA Catalogue
 - [-] Browse by Topic
 - [-] DEMOGRAPHY AND POPULATION
 - [-] ECONOMICS
 - [-] EDUCATION
 - [-] HEALTH
 - [-] HISTORY
 - [-] HOUSING AND LAND USE PLANNING
 - [-] INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS
 - [-] LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT
 - [-] LAW, CRIME AND LEGAL SYSTEMS
 - [-] NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
 - [-] POLITICS
 - [-] PSYCHOLOGY
 - [-] REFERENCE AND INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS
 - [-] SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
 - [-] SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GRADUAL MOBILITY
 - [-] SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS
 - [-] SOCIETY AND CULTURE
 - [-] TRADE, INDUSTRY AND MARKETS
 - [-] TRANSPORT, TRAVEL AND MOBILITY
 - [-] Browse by Keyword
 - [-] Browse by Data Publisher
 - ADP
 - ADPSS-Sociodata
 - CDSP
 - DANS
 - DDA
 - ESS
 - FORS
 - FSD
 - GESIS ZACAT
 - GSDB
 - NSD
 - NSD Metadata
 - SND
 - UKDA
 - WISDOM

Search Term: **SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS**

Study Section Variable

Study	Archive
Serviceundersökningen: Barnomsorg i fem typkommuner 1993	SND
Evaluation of the Independent Municipalities Project in Steinkjer, 1990	NSD Metadata
Survey on Level of Living and Social Network, 2007	NSD Metadata
ONS Omnibus Survey, Attitudes to Charities Module, July, August, September, October and November, 2006	UKDA
ONS Opinions Survey, Charitable Giving Module, February, June and October 2010 and February 2011	UKDA
ONS Omnibus Survey, October 2003	UKDA
ONS Omnibus Survey, July 2006	UKDA
ONS Omnibus Survey, October 2006	UKDA
ONS Omnibus Survey, June 2007	UKDA
Life Opportunities Survey: Wave One, 2009-2011	UKDA

1-10 of 63 | [Next](#) ▶

Narrower Terms:

- 🔍 social welfare policy (397 hits)
- 🔍 social welfare systems/structures (85 hits)
- 🔍 specific social services: use and provision (196 hits)

Search in Specific Language:

- 🔍 Sozialfürsorge, Sozialpolitik und Sozialsysteme (German) (3 hits)
- 🔍 SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS (English) (233 hits)

- ZACAT
 - ISSP
 - Eurobarometer
 - European Values Study (EVS)
 - Studies from Eastern Europe
 - ALLBUS (GGSS)
 - Politbarometer (German documentation only)
 - Election Studies (Germany)
 - Childhood, adolescence and becoming an adult 1991-1997 (bilingual documentation)
 - LebensRäume

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 - Election Studies (Germany)
 - Childhood, adolescence and becoming an adult 1991-1997 (bilingual documentation)
 - LebensRäume

ZACAT - GESIS Online Study Catalogue

Welcome to ZACAT, a social science data portal allowing you to search for, browse, analyse and download social science survey data, provided by [GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences](#) (dept. Data Archive for the Social Sciences).

The studies in this catalogue are a small selection of the added or recent

sets and without prior downloading
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analyse it online.
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ZACAT
and not the
provided for
able from the

respective link in the top-right menu.

Your [comments and remarks](#) are appreciated!

Recent Datasets / Collections
2012-07-11
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▶ ALLBUS - Kumulation 1980-2010 (ZA4574), version 1.0.0 (2012-05-22), doi:10.4232/1.11379▶ Eurobarometer 76.2 September-November 2011 (ZA5566), version 1.0.0 (2012-07-06), doi:10.4232/1.11388
2012-07-09
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▶ ISSP 2004: Citizenship (ZA3950), version 1.3.0 (2012-06-26), doi:10.4232/1.11372
2012-07-06
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▶ Eurobarometer 52.1 (ZA3205), version 2.0.0 (2012-06-05), doi:10.4232/1.11377▶ Eurobarometer 56.1 Social Exclusion and Modernization of Pension Systems (ZA3626), version 2.0.0 (2012-06-05), doi:10.4232/1.11378
2012-06-06
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▶ Lebensräume 2000-2010 (ZA5611), version 1.0.0 (2012-05-29), doi:10.4232/1.11374
Publication History ...

European Social Survey

ESS Round 1 - 2002
 ESS Round 2 - 2004
 ESS Round 3 - 2006
 ESS Round 4 - 2008
 Cumulative File
 Contextual Data
 Conditions of Use
 FAQ

ESS EduNet

ESS Bibliography

New User?

ESS Data archive

Norwegian Social Science
 Data Services (NSD)
 Harald Hårfagresgt. 29
 N-5007 Bergen
 Norway
 Phone: +47 555 82 117
 Fax: +47 555 89 650
essdata@nsd.uib.no

The European Social Survey

The European Social Survey (the ESS) is a biennial multi-country survey covering over 30 nations. The first round was fielded in 2002/2003, the fourth in 2008/2009.

The project is funded jointly by the European Commission, the European Science Foundation and academic funding bodies in each participating country, and is designed and carried out to exceptionally high standards. The project is directed by a Central Co-ordinating Team led by Roger Jowell at the Centre for Comparative Social Surveys, City University, London.

The questionnaire

The questionnaire includes two main sections, each consisting of approximately 120 items; a 'core' module which remains relatively constant from round to round, plus two or more 'rotating' modules, repeated at intervals. The core module aims to monitor change and continuity in a wide range of social variables, including media use; social and public trust; political interest and participation; socio-political orientations; governance and efficacy; moral; political and social values; social exclusion, national, ethnic and religious allegiances; well-being; health and security; human values; demographics and socio-economics.

Methodological data

The ESS collects a wide range of methodological data, including tests of reliability, call records, data on interview settings and event data.

Access to data

The data are available free of charge and without restrictions, for not-for-profit purposes. To access data files, you have to register as an ESS data user. If already registered, log in with your registered e-mail address as username. You don't have to log in to get access to the documentation files.

ESS Home Page

For further information about the ESS, please go to the [ESS Home Site](#).

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ESS Online Analysis

New ESS4 data release

The second edition of data and documentation for ESS round 4 was released 17.12.09.

Edition 2.0 includes Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russian Federation, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Parents' occupation files have also been released for the countries included in edition 2.0 of the main data file (listed above).

ESS round 4 includes rotating modules on the topics: Welfare attitudes in a changing Europe and Experiences and Expressions of Ageism. (17. Dec 09)

WEIGHTING DATA

Weighting is a very important concept in the analysis of sample data. Weighting allows you **to assign different weights to the different cases** in the analysis file. Weighting is usually **used to correct skewness** in a sample that is meant to represent a particular population.

Sample is weighted **to correct for deviations from national parameters**. Characteristics that might be used: region, the urban/rural divide, town size, household size, sex, age, occupation, education, marital status, and economic activity.

In probability sample surveys like the ESS, the essential characteristics of the sample design are captured by **design weights**. The design weight corrects for slightly different probabilities of selection, thereby making the sample more representative of a "true" sample of individuals. [ESS, 2012]

WEIGHTING DATA

In international data file you might find also a **Population Size weight**. This is used **when examining data for two or more countries combined**. This weight corrects for the fact that most countries taking part in the study had very similar sample sizes, no matter how large or small their population. The mathematics of probability proves that a sample of, for example, 1000 respondents is equally useful in examining the opinions in a country with 10 million inhabitants as it would be in a country with a population of only 1 million.

Without weighting, any figures combining two or more country's data would be incorrect, over-representing smaller countries at the expense of larger ones. So the *Population size* weight makes an adjustment to ensure that **each country is represented in proportion to its population size**. [ESS, 2012]

Why deposit data to data archives?

- » Assurance that data meet set quality standards
- » Long-term preservation of data in standardised accessible data formats
- » Safe-keeping of data in a secure environment with the ability to control access
- » Online resource discovery of data through data catalogues
- » Licensing arrangements to acknowledge data rights
- » Standardised citation mechanism to acknowledge data ownership
- » Promotion of data to many users

Why share research data?

Benefits Of Data Sharing To Researchers

- ✓ Assists in implementing publishers' data retention policies
- ✓ Increases visibility of scholarly work
- ✓ May enhance researchers' reputation
- ✓ May increase citations
open access journal articles cited two-three times more
- ✓ Enable collaborations on closely related themes, and new topics
- ✓ Establish links to next generation of researchers

Why share research data?

Benefits Of Data Sharing To Public And Funders

Public

- Production of high quality research with social value
- Advance science to the benefit of society
- Compliance with laws and regulations
- Adoption of emerging norms – ‘open access’ publishing
- To be, and appear to be, open and accountable

Funders

- Make optimal use of publicly funded research
- Avoid duplication of data collection
- Maximise return for investment

**If you have questions about access to data or data archiving
please contact me at**

<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

E-mail: arhiv.podatkov@fdv.uni-lj.si

